

QUINAZOLINES. PART I.

By TEJENDRA NATH GHOSH.

In a previous communication (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 124) the synthesis of the oxazine derivative (I) has been described. When heated with an aromatic amine at 160-170°, in presence of copper powder (*cf.* Narang and Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 976), the compound (I) furnishes the quinazoline (II). In this connection, reference is made to the synthesis of quinazolines by heating acetoanthranil with various amines (Anschutz, Schmidt and Greiffenberg, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 3482; Bogert and Beal, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **34**, 516, and subsequent papers).

When boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid, the compound (II, R = Ph) yields a mixture of hippuric acid and *o*-aminobenzanilide (*cf.* Bogert and Seil, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **28**, 890). In order to study the cyclisation of the compound (III) to (II), the hydrolysis of the compound (I) was tried, so that the corresponding acid could be utilised for the preparation of (III). The acid from (I), however, could not be obtained, because, as soon as it is liberated from the sodium salt by acid, it at once passes into (I).

For obvious pharmacological reasons, it seemed of considerable interest to synthesise a compound of the type (IV), in which an iminazole ring is fused with the quinazoline residue. When heated with *o*-phenylenediamine at 170-180° in presence of copper powder, the compound (I) yields (IV) with the elimination of two molecules of water (*cf.* Bistrzycki and Fässler, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1923, **6**, 525; Späth and Platzer, *Ber.*, 1936, **69**, 255).

The compound (IV) is stable towards concentrated hydrochloric acid and forms a hydrochloride.

It has been observed that, although the oxazine derivative (I) readily condenses with aldehydes in presence of acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate (Ghosh, *loc. cit.*), the quinazolines (II) and (IV) do not lend their apparently reactive methylene groups for condensation with aldehydes under similar conditions. In both cases, some steric influence may be responsible for this inactivity.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Keto-2-benzoylaminomethyl-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (II, R = Ph).—An intimate mixture of the compound (I, 5.6 g.) and aniline (1.9 g.) was melted at 185–190° and then copper powder (10 g.) was added. The mass was heated at 160–170° for 4 hours with occasional stirring. The dark mass was powdered and washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid and sodium carbonate solution. It was then extracted with hot alcohol; the alcoholic solution yielded on dilution with water a brownish solid which was twice crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 205°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: N, 11.91. $C_{22}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 11.83 per cent). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali, but dissolves in cold concentrated hydrochloric acid, being precipitated unchanged on standing or on dilution with water. It remains unchanged by the action of acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate.

The above compound was boiled with strong hydrochloric acid for about 2 hours and diluted with water. The clear solution was concentrated to a small bulk, when a crystalline mass was obtained which was filtered and triturated with cold water. The insoluble portion, on crystallisation from hot water, was proved to be hippuric acid. The aqueous solution on concentration yielded the hydrochloride (m.p. 183–84°); the free base was obtained from the hydrochloride by treatment with aqueous sodium acetate solution and crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 130°. Its identity with *o*-aminobenzanilide was confirmed by studying its properties and finally by analysis.

4-Keto-2-benzoylaminomethyl-3-p-tolyl-3,4-dihydroquinazoline (II, R = *p*-tolyl).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the previous compound. The compound crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 195–96°. (Found: N, 11.27. $C_{23}H_{19}O_2N_3$ requires N, 11.38 per cent). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali.

4-Kelo-2-benzoylaminomethyl-3-m-tolyl-3:4-dihydroquinazoline (II, R = *m*-tolyl).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the previous compound (II, R = phenyl). The compound crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 177-78°; yield nearly 50%. (Found: N, 11.50. $C_{23}H_{19}O_2N_3$ requires N, 11.38 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali.

Condensation of the Compound (I) with o-Phenylenediamine: Formation of 2-Benzoylaminomethyl-3:4-dihydroquinazoline-3:4-benzimidazole (IV).—An intimate mixture of the compound (I, 5.6 g.) and *o*-phenylenediamine (2.2 g.) was melted at 190° and then copper powder (10 g.) was added. The mass was heated at 170-180° for 4 hours. The dark mass was powdered and treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The acid solution was filtered and treated with excess of sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid, thus obtained, was dried and extracted with absolute alcohol; the alcoholic solution, on dilution with water, gave a brownish crystalline precipitate which was twice crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless needles, m.p. 211-12°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 74.78; H, 4.88; N, 16.12. $C_{22}H_{16}ON_4$ requires C, 75.0; H, 4.54; N, 15.91 per cent). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali. It does not contain any diazotisable amino group and does not form any acetyl derivative with acetic anhydride. It does not condense with phenyl isocyanate, indicating thereby the absence of any free amino group.

The above compound dissolves in dilute hydrochloric acid and the solution, on evaporation, yields the hydrochloride in the form of colourless plates, m.p. 225-31°. The hydrochloride was found contaminated with slight gummy matter, which, however, could not be removed by several crystallisations. When treated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution, it yields the original compound (IV). The compound (IV) has been found to remain stable when boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid for about 45 minutes, the above hydrochloride being formed by this treatment.

Condensation of the Compound (I) with o-Nitroaniline.—Following the above method, the condensation was tried in presence of copper powder at 170-180° and at higher temperatures, but the condensation could not be effected.

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DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

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